

Polarographic Studies on 2-Mercaptoethanol

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Polarographic behaviour of 2-mercaptoethanol (RSH) is studied at dme in 0.1M HClO₄, Britton-Robinson buffers of pH 2.0-11.9 and 0.1M NaOH. Only a pre-wave with its height directly proportional to the concentration of the depolarizer is obtained if RSH concentration is $>2 \times 10^{-4}$ M. An anodic wave associated with a pre-wave is obtained at all pH values if RSH concentration is $<2 \times 10^{-4}$ M. The pre-wave does not merge in the main wave on increasing the pH. The diffusion coefficient in a buffer of pH 2.0 calculated using Ilkovic equation is 7.03×10^{-6} cm² sec⁻¹ and the dissociation constant of sulphhydryl group is 6.45. The anodic wave produced is due to diffusion controlled one-electron reversible charge transfer process and the product of oxidation is a mercurous compound (RSH)₂Hg which gets converted quickly to (RS)₂Hg.

RECENTLY, a distinct pre-wave associated with the main anodic wave has been observed in the polarographic studies on 2- and 3-mercaptopropionic acids¹ though Saxena and coworkers^{2,3} have reported only a single reversible anodic wave. No pre-wave has been reported for θ -aminobenzenethiol⁴. In continuation of the electrochemical investigations of mercaptans the polarographic behaviour of 2-mercaptoethanol was studied at the dropping mercury electrode.

Experimental

2-Mercaptoethanol (Fluka) and other chemicals of analytical grade were used as such. The solution of 2-mercaptoethanol was prepared in air-free conductivity water and standardized against chloramine-T⁵.

The polarograph, the capillary characteristics, methods of preparation of various solutions and that of running the polarograms have already been reported⁴. Temperature was maintained at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$ except for the study on the effect of temperature.

Results and Discussion

The effects of pH, 2-mercaptoethanol (RSH) concentration, mercury height and the composition of the medium are investigated with a view to recognise the characteristics of the wave. The electrolysis of RSH in buffered solutions and the polarographic analysis of the compound thus obtained are carried out to understand the mechanism of the reaction at the electrode surface.

Effect of pH: 2-Mercaptoethanol (10^{-3} M) in 0.1M HClO₄, Britton-Robinson buffers of pH 2.0-11.9 and 0.1M-NaOH, all containing 0.1M KNO₃, gives an anodic wave which is associated with a pre-wave at more negative potential (Fig. 1). Such a pre-wave has not been observed during the study of θ -aminobenzenethiol⁴. The pre-wave in the present

Fig. 1. Polarograms of 10^{-3} M 2-mercaptoethanol in different buffers.

(i) 0.1M HClO₄, (ii) pH 2.0, (iii) pH 3.0, (iv) pH 4.0, (v) pH 5.0, (vi) pH 6.0, (vii) pH 7.0, (viii) pH 8.0, (ix) pH 9.0, (x) pH 10.0, (xi) pH 10.9, (xii) pH 11.9, (xiii) 0.1M NaOH

study does not merge in the main wave on increasing the pH as is observed in the case of 2- and 3-mercaptopropionic acids¹. However, increase in pH shifts the waves to more negative potentials and the difference in their half-wave potentials decreases gradually. The diffusion plateaus are well defined at pH higher than 4.0 and are increasingly drawn out in more acidic solutions. The total diffusion current is noticeably less in higher pH buffers.

Polarograms of 2-mercaptoethanol (10^{-3} M) recorded in McIlvaine buffers as well as in Clark and Lubs buffers of pH 2.2, 6.0 and 8.0 indicate that the shape and nature of the waves are dependent upon the pH value but are independent of the composition of the buffer. The concentration of KNO₃ in solutions containing buffers of pH 2.0-11.9 does not affect the nature and shape of the polarograms.

Effect of RSH concentration: In the polarographic curves of RSH ($>2 \times 10^{-4}$ M) recorded in 0.1M HClO₄, Britton-Robinson buffers of pH 2.0-11.9 and 0.1M NaOH only a pre-wave with its height

directly proportional to the concentration of the depolarizer is obtained. With further increase in concentration the main anodic wave starts forming and the increase in concentration increases only its height so that the sum of the pre-wave and the main wave height remains proportional to the depolarizer concentration (Table 1). *o*-Aminobenzenethiol

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF 2-MERCAPTOETHANOL ON THE WAVE HEIGHTS IN BRITTON-ROBINSON BUFFER OF pH 2.0

Concentration (C) × 10 ⁻³ M	Pre-wave height (i _a) μA	i _a / C	Total wave height (i _d) μA	i _d / C	I = $\frac{i_d}{Cm^{2/3}t^{1/6}}$
0.05	0.16	3.20	0.16	3.20	1.58
0.10	0.35	3.30	0.33	3.30	1.63
0.20	0.64	3.20	0.64	3.20	1.58
0.40	0.64	1.60	1.29	3.26	1.59
0.60	0.64	1.07	1.96	3.27	1.61
1.00	0.64	0.64	3.28	3.28	1.62
2.00	0.64	0.32	6.62	3.31	1.63

Mean I = 1.61

gives only one anodic wave at concentrations lower than 2 × 10⁻⁴ M. At higher concentrations this wave splits up into more than one wave but none of them is adsorption controlled⁴. The half-wave potential of both the waves in the present study is independent of the depolarizer concentration indicating that the reaction product at the electrode surface is soluble and the electrode reaction is reversible.

2-Mercaptoethanol can be conveniently estimated polarographically over the entire pH range in 0.1M KNO₃. Its diffusion coefficient in a buffer of pH 2.0 calculated from Ilkovič equation is 7.03 × 10⁻⁶ cm² sec⁻¹.

Effect of mercury height (h_{corr}): The effect of the h_{corr} on the wave height/s is studied in all the solutions. As in the case of mercaptopropionic acids¹, the sum of the wave heights in the present study is proportional to √h_{corr} indicating diffusion controlled nature of the anodic reaction. The limiting height of the pre-wave (i_a) alone, however, is proportional to h_{corr} which is in keeping with the adsorption nature of this wave. In the cases where there is no pre-wave in the polarograms of 2-mercaptoethanol, the height of the main anodic wave (i_d) is proportional to √h_{corr}. The E_{1/2} of the anodic waves is independent of the Hg height suggesting the reversibility of the reaction (Table 2).

Effect of temperature: Polarographic curves are recorded in a buffer of pH 7.0 at different temperatures in the range 25-50° (Table 3). The magnitude of the difference in half-wave potentials of the pre-wave and the main wave decreases with increase in temperature and only a single wave is observed at temperature above 50°. This lends further support to the adsorption nature of the pre-wave.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF MERCURY HEIGHT ON WAVE HEIGHTS OF 2-MERCAPTOETHANOL (10⁻³ M) IN pH 3.0 IN 50% ETHANOL

[h_{soln} = 3.00 cm (= 0.220 cm of Hg);

$$\text{back pressure} = \frac{3.1}{(1.998 \times 4.40)^{1/3}} = 1.509$$

Hg cm	h _{corr} cm	i _d	$\frac{i_d}{\sqrt{h_{corr}}}$	-E _{1/2} V (vs SCE)
50	48.277	2.51	0.361	0.265
55	53.277	2.62	0.359	0.265
60	58.277	2.75	0.360	0.265
65	63.277	2.84	0.357	0.265
70	68.277	2.97	0.357	0.265
76	74.277	3.07	0.359	0.265

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE WAVE CHARACTERISTICS OF 2-MERCAPTOETHANOL (10⁻³ M) IN pH 7.0

Temp. °C	i _d	$\frac{i_d(\text{ambient})}{i_d(25^\circ)}$	Temp. co-efficient % per °C	-E _{1/2} V (vs SCE)
25	2.76	1.00	—	0.355
30	2.82	1.02	1.227	0.355
35	2.93	1.06	1.229	0.355
40	3.01	1.09	1.223	0.355
45	3.13	1.13	1.226	0.355
50	3.24	1.19	1.228	0.350

Mean Temp. Co-efficient = 1.226 °C⁻¹

The mean value of the temperature coefficient calculated by Nejedly's method⁶ is 1.226 °C⁻¹. The linearity of i_d with temperature and constancy of temperature coefficient show that the height of the entire anodic wave is solely controlled by diffusion. That the half-wave potential remains independent of temperature is in keeping with the reversible nature of the electrode process.

Effect of ethanol concentration: The pre-wave tends to merge with the main wave in 0.1M HClO₄ solutions containing ethanol and only one wave is observed if ethanol concentration is more than 50% (Fig. 2) confirming the adsorption nature of the

Fig. 2. Polarograms of 10⁻³ M 2-mercaptoethanol in (a) 20%, (b) 30%, (c) 40%, (d) 50% and (e) 60% Ethanol in pH 3.0.

wave. It also indicates that the tendency of the reaction product at dme to get adsorbed on to the mercury drop decreases with increasing ethanol concentration. The total limiting diffusion current decreases with increase in ethanol concentration and becomes practically constant when the solution contains 50% or more ethanol. The half-wave potential of the single wave obtained in solutions containing more than 50% ethanol is independent of ethanol concentration.

Mechanism of anodic reaction : Since a plot of $E_{d.e.}$ vs $\log \left(\frac{i_d - i}{i}\right)^2$ for polarograms in solutions containing buffer of pH more than 6.0 for all concentrations of 2-mercaptoethanol (at 50°) does not yield a straight line with a slope of 29.5 mV (Fig. 3, i) it may be concluded that the reaction does not proceed according to the following equation :

The fact that the half-wave potential is independent of RSH concentration in a buffer of pH 2.0 and in 0.1M HClO₄ further rules out the possibility of the above reaction. This constancy of half-wave potential is characteristic of equation :

$$E_{d.e.} = E_{\frac{1}{2}} - 0.059 \log \frac{i_d - i}{i} \quad \dots (2)$$

Furthermore, a plot of $E_{d.e.}$ vs $\log \frac{i_d - i}{i}$ yields a straight line with a slope of 54-56 mV at 50° (Fig. 3, ii). This value is fairly close to the theoretical value for one electron transfer process at this temperature suggesting that the reaction is reversible and proceeds through either Eq. (3) or (4)

Fig. 3. Plots of $E_{d.e.}$ vs $\log \frac{(i_d - i)^2}{i}$ (curve i) and

$$E_{d.e.} \text{ vs } \log \frac{i_d - i}{i} \text{ (curve ii).}$$

An aliquot of the solution obtained on electrolyzing $10^{-3}M$ RSH to completion in a buffer of pH 7.0 at a potential of 0.0V on a large Hg pool electrode in an inert atmosphere for about 4 hrs

gives a black turbidity with hydrogen sulphide gas showing the presence of soluble mercury. Another part of the electrolyzed solution on being polarographed under similar conditions gives a cathodic wave corresponding to one electron reversible charge transfer process (Fig. 4, i). A mixture of the electrolyzed solution and $10^{-3}M$ RSH on being electrolyzed at a temperature higher than 50°, gives

Fig. 4. Comparative anodic cathodic C-V curves of 2-mercaptoethanol and its oxidation product at mercury electrode in buffer of pH 7.0 and at 50°.

- (i) $10^{-3}M$ RSH solution after being electrolyzed completely at large mercury pool electrode,
- (ii) $10^{-3}M$ RSH,
- (iii) Solution of curve i + $10^{-3}M$ RSH,
- (iv) $10^{-3}M$ RSH + $5 \times 10^{-4}M$ HgCl₂.

a composite wave; a cathodic part due to the reduction of the oxidation product and an anodic part because of the oxidation of RSH (Fig. 4, iii). These observations show that the reaction mechanism indicated by Eq. (1) or (3) is untenable. The reaction proceeds through Eq. (4) and the product of anodic oxidation is a soluble compound of mercury with RSH. The solubility of the reaction product is inferred from the observation that half-wave potential is independent of RSH concentration. The formation of composite wave also supports the reversible nature of the electrode reaction. An 1 : 1 mixture of $10^{-3}M$ RSH and $5 \times 10^{-4}M$ HgCl₂ yields a well defined cathodic wave (Fig. 4, iv) having the same characteristics as that obtained for the reduction of the oxidized product at dropping mercury electrode (Fig. 4, i). A solution containing $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ RSH and $5 \times 10^{-4}M$ HgCl₂ yields a composite wave similar to that in Fig. 4, iii. This shows that the product of electrode reaction is a mercury compound and mercury and RSH combine in the ratio 1 : 2.

$10^{-3}M$ RSH in a buffer of pH 2.0 and pre-saturated with Hg₂Cl₂ gives a wave similar to the

one given by an 1 : 1 mixture of $10^{-3} M$ RSH and $4.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ $HgCl_2$, indicating that the species being reduced in both the cases is the same i.e., $(RS)_2Hg$. The cathodic wave is, however, given by the reduction of an unstable RSHg, apparently the reaction

is very rapid so that RSHg is the compound being reduced at the dropping mercury electrode.

It may, therefore, be concluded that RSH is not being oxidized to disulphide but it depolarizes the

mercury electrode with the formation of unstable RSHg. The reduction wave of $(RS)_2Hg$ corresponds to the reduction of univalent cation and hence the reaction proceeds through Eqs. (4) and (5).

Determination of dissociation constant: The half-wave potential of the single wave obtained by plotting $E_{1/2}$ vs $\log \frac{i_d - i}{i}$ for polarograms of $2 \times 10^{-4} M$ RSH (for waves obtained at 50°) on plotting against pH values, gives two linear portions intersecting at a point corresponding to pH 6.45 (Fig. 5). The dissociation constant of sulphhydryl group is, therefore, 6.45. However, in solutions with pH above 6.45, the half-wave potential remains constant showing that the hydrogen ions are no more involved in the electrode reactions in these media.

Fig. 5. Plot of $E_{1/2}$ of 2-mercaptoethanol as a function of pH.

References

1. R. PARKASH, R. S. VERMA and N. KUMAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **14**, 997.
2. R. S. SAXENA, P. SINGH and M. L. MITTAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 1149.
3. R. S. SAXENA and K. C. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 101.
4. R. PARKASH, R. K. KALIA, R. P. SINGH and N. KUMAR, *Mh. Chem.*, 1977, **108**, 589.
5. R. C. PAUL, S. K. SHARMA, N. KUMAR and R. PARKASH, *Talanta*, 1975, **22**, 311.
6. V. NEJEDLY, *Collect. Czechosl. Chem. Commun.*, 1929, **1**, 319.